

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF SOME TIPS AND STRATEGIES OF IELTS WRITING

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Annotation. Writing a compelling essay in IELTS Writing requires more than just a good command of language. It demands the use of effective writing strategies that can help organize your ideas, develop arguments and show case your writing skills. To achieve this, it is recommended to start by carefully analyzing the essay prompt and identifying the key points that need to be addressed. Then plan your essay structure, including the introduction, body paragraphs, and conclusion. Use relevant evidence to support your arguments and ensure coherence and clarity throughout your essay to eliminate any grammatical errors and ensure that your writing effectively communicates your message to the reader.

Key words: Pie chart, bar chart, line graph, table, mixed, advantage and disadvantage, agree or disagree, discussion and opinion essay, fluctuation.

IELTS Writing test is made to assess your writing skills and techniques. There are two IELTS Writing modules: Academic and General. If you plan to study abroad, then you should take IELTS Academic module. And if you wish to work abroad, then you should take IELTS General module.

IELTS Writing test lasts 1 hour and consists of 2 parts: task 1 and task 2. Writing task 1 is different for Academic and General IELTS, but Writing task 2 is the same for both modules.

In Academic Writing task 1 you are asked to describe a graph, chart or diagram. And in General Writing task 1 you have to write a letter to someone. In Writing task 2 you have to write an essay on a given topic.

IELTS Academic Writing

IELTS Academic Writing module lasts 60 minutes and has 2 tasks, which must both be completed. Although it is recommended to spend approximately 20

minutes on task 1 and about 40 minutes on task 2, you can divide your time between two sections the way you prefer.

Task 1

You have about 20 minutes

You must write a report of at least 150 words

You are given a visual presentation which can be in form of a graph, diagram, bar chart, table, map or a process. You must write a report explaining the main features of the figure and make comparisons where relevant. You must not include any personal opinion while you are explaining the figure. You just need to describe and report what you are given.

How to use your 20 minutes

You have 20 minutes for task 1, so try spending 5 minutes on each paragraph. This might help you to organise your time better.

First 5 minutes

Read the question, make sure you understand the chart, write your introduction by paraphrasing the question.

Second 5 minutes

Look at the chart and try to find 2 general points. Don't look at specific details; look for "the big picture". Write 2 sentences summarising the information.

Final 10 minutes

Describe specific details. Try to break this part into 2 paragraphs because it looks better. You could spend 5 minutes on each paragraph.

Task 2 involves writing an essay on the given topic. You have to answer the questions clearly and completely;

give reasons for your answer;

include relevant example from your knowledge, from your experience

spend about 40 minutes on the task

write at least 250 words/260-265

The Answer Sheet

The last two pages of the IELTS Writing answer sheet are dedicated to task two and together have over 40 lines. Although you may ask for extra sheets to write your answer in, this is not likely to become necessary since the space you are already provided with is way more than sufficient. You must not write in the blank space at the bottom of the first page or in the scoring section at the bottom of page two.

Focus on Academic Register

Use longer sentences (about 20-30 words)

Use subordinate clauses

Use academic words(see "The Academic Words List" at www.tahasani.com/resources)

Avoid contractions like doesn't,can't or they'll

Avoid phrasal verbs where possible

Avoid over-generalization by avoiding absolute statements and introducing probability/possibility

Task Types

Opinion-led

a) New parents should attend parenting classes to learn how to bring up their children well.To what extent do you agree or disagree with this statement

b) Some people think that every individual is responsible for their own healthy lifestyle.Others believe that governments should take care of it.what are your views on this?

c) Many parents now let their young children use tablet computers to see pictures and photographs,watch videos or play games.

Is this a positive or negative development?

Argument discussion

a) Some people believe that children should listen to and obey their parents.Others believe that children should think and do things on their own.

Discuss both these views and give your own opinion.

b) While some people prefer to live in apartments,others do not think an apartment is a suitable form of accommodation.

Do you think the advantages of living in an apartment outweigh the disadvantages?

Issue Discussion

a) Housing and accommodation has become a major problem in many countries around the world.

What are some of the main factors that have contributed to this problem?

b) While mobile phones have many advantages,a number of problems have also resulted from them or the ways in which they are used.

What are some of these problems?

What solutions can you suggest for solving these problems?

c) Nowadays most people choose to throw away broken things instead of repairing them,and replace them with new ones.

Why is this happening?

What problems may it lead to?

Mixed(Two-Part)Questions

In some countries people prefer to buy used things rather than new ones.Why is this the case?

Is it a positive or negative trend?

In summary,in this article, it has been provided detailed information about the types and strategies of writing ,as well as information on how to improve writing skills. Moreover knowing all details about specific peculiarities of writing might help the candidates or learners in the certain field, English as foreign language effectively. On the other hand ,following the rules required time management for both types of writing is also crucial.

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